

A Hospital-Based Study Evaluating Clinical and Echocardiographic Assessment of Patients with Atrial FibrillationBirendra Kumar¹, Gitanjali kumari²¹Assistant Professor, Department of General Medicine, Jannayak Karpuri Thakur Medical College and Hospital, Madhepura, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Department of Radiology, Jannayak Karpuri Thakur Medical College and Hospital, Madhepura, Bihar, India

Received: 20-06-2023 / Revised 06-07-2023 / Accepted 12-08-2023

Corresponding author: Dr. Birendra Kumar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Aim:** The aim of the present study was to assess the clinical and echocardiographic assessment of patients with atrial fibrillation.**Methods:** The present study was conducted in the Department of General Medicine for 2 years. 200 patients, 80 males and 120 females were included in this study.**Results:** The most common symptom was dyspnoea 75% followed by Congestive cardiac failure 70%. There was history of mild to moderate chest pain in 12% of patients. 17% of patients had history of syncope/dizzy spells. Fatigability was noticed in 20% cases. Majority of patients, 55% had RHD as underlying cause of atrial fibrillation. There were 40% females and 60% males in this group. 9% patients had coronary artery disease. Hypertension alone was present in 7% of patients. 9% of patients had COPD as a risk factor. 8% of patients had cardiomyopathy. Hyperthyroidism was found in 3% of patients. 72% patients had heart rates >100. Fibrillatory P wave was seen in 23% patients and absent p waves in 78% of patients. LVH was seen in 12% patients, RVH in 30% patients, RBBB in 5% patients, and LBBB in 6% patients, ST depression and T wave inversion in 60% patients. The maximum number of patients i.e. 36% had LA dimension between 4.1-5.0 cm².**Conclusion:** In our study dyspnoea was the commonest symptom in atrial fibrillation and rheumatic heart disease was the major aetiological factor. Patient with left atrial dimension >4.0 cm had sustained atrial fibrillation. Thromboembolic phenomenon was more common in chronic AF and all the patients had mitral valve disease.**Keywords:** Cardiomyopathy, Atrial Fibrillation, Rheumatic Heart Disease.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Atrial fibrillation (AF) is a common supraventricular tachyarrhythmia affecting 1% to 2% of the general population. [1] The risk of AF generally increases with aging, hypertension, coronary artery disease, diabetes mellitus, alcohol use. [2,3] However, the valvular disease is the most common substrate for AF in areas with a high prevalence of rheumatic heart disease and is a risk factor for embolic stroke and heart failure. [4,5] The cardiac remodeling that occurs in response to various causes tends to increase the left atrial pressure and size and alter wall stress creating a substrate to cause AF. [6-8] The enlarged left atrium (LA) has been correlated with AF occurrence and cardiovascular events. [9,10] The left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) is also associated with AF development and its consequences. [11,12]

Atrial fibrillation (AF) is the most common sustained arrhythmia and is responsible for almost 300 000 hospital admissions annually. [13] Its prevalence increases from 1% among those 60 years old to almost 9% among octogenarians. [14] Characterized by lack of organized atrial electrical and mechanical activity, AF is typically associated with a rapid ventricular response that results in alterations in the patient's clinical and hemodynamic state. The loss of atrial systolic contribution to total left ventricular filling leads to depressed cardiac output and symptoms of dyspnea and fatigue. [15] In addition, the resulting stasis of blood, enhanced platelet aggregation, and coagulation [16] predisposes to the formation of atrial thrombi and subsequent thromboembolism, [15,16] the most feared complication of AF.

Electrocardiographic risk factors include left axis deviation, left ventricular hypertrophy, ischemic

changes and Echocardiographic risk factors include left atrial enlargement, increased left ventricular wall thickness and decreased left ventricular fractional shortening. Various common complications associated with Atrial Fibrillation include Congestive cardiac failure. at rest approximately 20% of left ventricular stroke volume is by atrial contraction which will be lost in AF and hence LV dysfunction can occur. [17] The most common complication in AF is thromboembolism-induced stroke. AF is associated with 5 fold increased risk of stroke than in unaffected population. Older patients are not only more prone to AF but their risk of stroke is considerably increased as compared to younger patients with AF. [18]

The aim of the present study was to assess the clinical and echocardiographic assessment of patients with atrial fibrillation.

Materials and Methods

The present study was conducted in the Department of General Medicine, Jannayak Karpuri Thakur Medical College and Hospital Madhepura, Bihar, India for 2 years, 200 patients, 80 males and 120 females were included in this study. All patients were requested to participate and after taking consent they were investigated historically and

clinically to find out cause and complication of atrial fibrillation as per semi structured question are(annexure). Out of 100 patients 70 were those who attended OPD and rest were 30 indoor patients The patients were screened for the underlying causes, leading to AF and correlated clinically and echocardiographically. Detailed history was recorded in each case paying special attention to history regarding symptoms of AF like palpitation, chest pain, dyspnoea, orthopnoea, paroxysmal nocturnal dyspnoea, sweating, nausea and vomiting, cough, fever, haemoptysis, dizziness, syncope, weakness, easy fatigability, neurodeficit, sudden blindness, tremors smoking and alcohol intake. A detailed history was also taken regarding the presence of other co-morbid conditions like hypertension, rheumatic heart disease, thyrotoxicosis, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, old stroke, coronary artery disease and re-current congestive heart failure. A complete physical, systemic and laboratory examination was done on each patient. A detailed systemic examination was done with special emphasis on cardiovascular system - examination. Echocardiography was performed on AF patients by an experienced cardiologist.

Results

Table 1: Various Mode of Presentation of Patients with Atrial Fibrillation

Symptoms	No. of patients	Percentage
Dyspnoea NYHA Class II – IV)	150	75
Congestive cardiac failure	140	70
Palpitation	116	58
Fatigue	40	20
Syncope/ Dizzy spells	34	17
None	28	14
Chest pain	24	12

The most common symptom was dyspnoea 75% followed by Congestive cardiac failure 70%. There was history of mild to moderate chest pain in 12% of patients. 17% of patients had history of syncope/dizzy spells. Fatigability was noticed in 20% cases.

Table 2: Clinical Characteristics According to Cause of Atrial Fibrillation

Risk factors	Male	%	Female	%	Total	%
RHD	30	15	80	40	110	55
HTN (alone)	8	4	6	3	14	7
COPD	14	7	4	2	18	9
Coronary artery disease	12	6	6	3	18	9
Cardiomyopathy	12	6	4	2	16	8
Congenital heart diseases	0	0	4	2	4	2
Hyperthyroidism	0	0	6	3	6	3
Lone AF	4	2	10	5	14	7
Total	80	40	120	60	200	100

Majority of patients, 55% had RHD as underlying cause of atrial fibrillation. There were 40% females and 60% females in this group. 9% patients had coronary artery disease. Hypertension alone was present in 7% of patients. 9% of patients had COPD as a risk factor. 8% of patients had cardiomyopathy Hyperthyroidism was found in 3% of patients.

Table 3: ECG Findings of Patients with Atrial Fibrillation

ECG findings	No. of patients	Percentage
Heart Rate > 100	144	72
< 100	64	32
Fibrillary waves	46	23
Absent 'p' waves	160	80
RBBB	10	5
LBBB	12	6
ST depression/'T' wave inversion	120	60
LVH	24	12
RVH	60	30

72% patients had heart rates >100. Fibrillary P wave was seen in 23% patients and absent p waves in 78% of patients. LVH was seen in 12% patients, RVH in 30% patients, RBBB in 5% patients, and LBBB in 6% patients, ST depression and T wave inversion in 60% patients.

Table 4: Left Atrial Dimensions

LA Dimensions	No. of patients	Percentage
< 4.0 cm ²	60	30
4.1 – 5.0 cm ²	72	36
> 5.0 cm ²	64	32

The maximum number of patients i.e. 36% had LA dimension between 4.1-5.0 cm².

Discussion

Atrial Fibrillation (AF) is one of the commonest arrhythmia seen in clinical practice. The incidence is 0.5% in patients under 60 years of age and 10% in patients above the age of 80 years. In Western countries, elderly population is at risk, but in countries like India where rheumatic heart disease (RHD) is rampant, it is the commonest cause of mortality and morbidity in the young. [19] 15% of all strokes are related to AF associated with thromboembolic events. [20] Electrophysiologically, AF represents disorganized atrial depolarization that results from chronic wavelets of re-entry. The various causes of AF that have been suggested are damage to sino atrial node and internodal pathways, atrial dilatation and occlusion of the nodal artery. [21]

The most common symptom was dyspnoea 75% followed by Congestive cardiac failure 70%. There was history of mild to moderate chest pain in 12% of patients. 17% of patients had history of syncope/dizzy spells. Fatigability was noticed in 20% cases. Majority of patients, 55% had RHD as underlying cause of atrial fibrillation. There were 40% females and 60% males in this group. Tischler et al [22] reported dyspnoea in 62% of patients, palpitation in 33% patients, and syncope in 12% patients in a similar study. Flaker et al [23] in their study observed that 78% patients had dyspnoea and 11 % had chest pain at presentation whereas Levey et al [24] reported that 54.1% patients had palpitation, 44.4% patients had dyspnoea and 10.1% patients had chest pain. Fatigue was noted in 14.3% patients. 9% patients had coronary artery disease. Hypertension alone

was present in 7% of patients. 9% of patients had COPD as a risk factor. 8% of patients had cardiomyopathy. Hyperthyroidism was found in 3% of patients. In India, a study conducted by Singh et al [25] reported RHD in 37.87%, cardiomyopathy in 13.6%, HTN in 3%, IHD in 3.03%, thyrotoxicosis in 9.05% and lone fibrillation in 1.5% of their patients. Kumar et al [26] reported RHD in 39%, IHD in 29%, HTN in 54%, cardiomyopathy in 4%, COPD in 3% and thyrotoxicosis in 5% of their patients. Timane et al [27] showed RHD in 55% patients, cardiomyopathy in 11.25%, thyrotoxicosis and COPD in 8.75% each. Studies conducted by Levey et al [24] reported RHD in 15.2%, non-rheumatic valvular lesion in 3.3%, cardiomyopathy in 14%, hypertensive heart disease in 21.4%, IHD in 16.6%, thyrotoxicosis in 3.1%, and COPD in 11.2% as the various causes of atrial fibrillation. Kannel et al [28] reported RHD in 54.08% respectively and found that RHD was the most common cause of AF.

72% patients had heart rates >100. Fibrillary P wave was seen in 23% patients and absent p waves in 78% of patients. LVH was seen in 12% patients, RVH in 30% patients, RBBB in 5% patients, and LBBB in 6% patients, ST depression and T wave inversion in 60% patients. The maximum number of patients i.e. 36% had LA dimension between 4.1-5.0 cm². Henry et al [29] (observed if left atrial dimension exceeded 4.5 cm², cardioversion was unlikely to be effective in the long run. Left atrial size >4.0cm² is the single strongest predictor of increased risk of embolization. Cabin et al and Blackshear et al [30,31] and according to Sandflippo et al [32] atrial size is increased in time with atrial fibrillation even in the absence of other causes of atrial enlargement. In a study done by A.

Banerjee et al [33], it was seen that EF measurement alone was not helpful in predicting the risk of stroke/ Thromboembolism in patients of Non Valvular AF with Heart Failure. Presence of abnormal EF (LV systolic dysfunction) independently predicts the risk of stroke as shown by Atrial fibrillation investigators study. [34] It was observed in a study done by Mahmood ul Hassan that significant correlation was observed for LA clot in patients with AF and LA size \geq 45 mm, ($p > 0.001$). Out of 1544 patients taken, the mean LA size was 43.82 ± 2.12 mm. Atrial fibrillation was observed in 289 patients (18.7%). Overall clot was seen in 224 (14.5%) patients. Left atrial appendage clot was seen in 202 (89.73%) and LA clot was seen in 9 patients (4.02%). [35]

Conclusion

In our study dyspnoea was the commonest symptom in atrial fibrillation and rheumatic heart disease was the major aetiological factor. Patient with left atrial dimension > 4.0 cm had sustained atrial fibrillation. Thromboembolic phenomenon was more common in chronic AF and all the patients had mitral valve disease.

References

1. Kannel WB, Abbott RD, Savage DD, McNamara PM. Epidemiologic features of chronic atrial fibrillation: the Framingham study. *N Engl J Med.* 1982 Apr 29;306(17):1018–22.
2. Benjamin EJ, Levy D, Vaziri SM, Agostino RBD, Belanger AJ, Wolf PA. Independent risk factors for atrial fibrillation in a population-based cohort. The Framingham Heart Study. *JAMA.* 1994 Mar 16;271(11):840–4.
3. Marcus GM, Alonso A, Peralta CA, Lettre G, Vittinghoff E, Lubitz SA, et al. European ancestry as a risk factor for atrial fibrillation in African Americans. *Circulation.* 2010 Nov 16;122(20):2009–15.
4. Diker E, Aydogdu S, Ozdemir M, Kural T, Polat K, Cehreli S, et al. Prevalence and predictors of atrial fibrillation in rheumatic valvular heart disease. *Am J Cardiol.* 1996 Jan 1;77(1):96–8.
5. Camm AJ, Lip GYH, De Caterina R, Savelieva I, Atar D, Hohnloser SH, et al. 2012 focused update of the ESC Guidelines for the management of atrial fibrillation: an update of the 2010 ESC Guidelines for the management of atrial fibrillation. Developed with the special contribution of the European Heart Rhythm Association. *Eur Heart J.* 2012 Nov;33(21):2719–47.
6. Nattel S. New ideas about atrial fibrillation 50 years on. *Nature.* 2002 Jan;415(6868):219–26.
7. Cohn JN, Ferrari R, Sharpe N. Cardiac remodeling—concepts and clinical implications: a consensus paper from an international forum on cardiac remodeling. Behalf of an International Forum on Cardiac Remodeling. *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 2000 Mar 1;35(3):569–82.
8. January CT, Wann LS, Alpert JS, Calkins H, Cigarroa JE, Cleveland Jr JC, et al. 2014 AHA/ACC/HRS guideline for the management of patients With atrial fibrillation: executive summary: a report of the American College of Cardiology/ American Heart Association Task Force on practice guidelines and the Heart Rhythm Society. *Circulation.* 2014 Dec 2;130(23):2071–104.
9. Vaziri SM, Larson MG, Benjamin EJ, Levy D. Echocardiographic predictors of non-rheumatic atrial fibrillation. The Framingham Heart Study. *Circulation.* 1994 Feb; 89(2):724–30.
10. Bouzas-Mosquera A, Brouillon FJ, Alvarez-Garcia N, Mendez E, Peteiro J, Gandara-Sambade T, et al. Left atrial size and risk for all-cause mortality and ischemic stroke. *CMAJ.* 2011 Jul 12;183(10):E657–64.
11. Seko Y, Kato T, Haruna T, Izumi T, Miyamoto S, Nakane, E et al. Association between atrial fibrillation, atrial enlargement, and left ventricular geometric remodeling. *Sci Rep.* 2018 Apr;8(1):6366.
12. Tsang TS, Barnes ME, Bailey KR, Leibson CL, Montgomery SC, Takemoto Y, et al. Left atrial volume: important risk marker of incident atrial fibrillation in 1655 older men and women. *Mayo Clin Proc.* 2001 May;76(5):467–75.
13. American Heart Association. Heart and Stroke Facts: Statistical Supplement. Dallas, Tex: American Heart Association. *Circulation.* 1998; 98:11–1016.
14. Vaziri SM, Larson MG, Benjamin EJ, Levy D. Echocardiographic predictors of nonrheumatic atrial fibrillation. The Framingham Heart Study. *Circulation.* 1994 Feb;89(2):724–30.
15. Pritchett EL. Management of atrial fibrillation. *New England Journal of Medicine.* 1992 May 7;326(19):1264–71.
16. Sohara H, Amitani S, Kurose M, Miyahara K. Atrial fibrillation activates platelets and coagulation in a time-dependent manner: a study in patients with paroxysmal atrial fibrillation. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology.* 1997 Jan;29(1):106–12.
17. Grogan M, Smith HC, Gersh BJ, Wood DL. Left ventricular dysfunction due to atrial fibrillation in patients initially believed to have idiopathic dilated cardiomyopathy. *Am J Cardiol.* 1992;69(19):1570–3.
18. Sastry KBR, Kumar LS, Anuradha P, Raj B, Afzal MAM. Clinical profile and Echocardiographic findings in patients with Atrial Fibrillation. *IJSRP.* 2016,6(2):44–7.

19. Ray B. Acute management of atrial fibrillation: the commonest arrhythmia in clinical practice. *Journal of the Indian Medical Association*. 2004 Apr 1;102(4):209-10.
20. Cabin HS, Clubb KS, Hall C, Perlmutter RA, Feinstein AR. Risk for systemic embolization of atrial fibrillation without mitral stenosis. *The American journal of cardiology*. 1990 May 1;65(16):1112-6.
21. Davies MJ, Pomerance A. Pathology of atrial fibrillation in man. *British Heart Journal*. 1972 May;34(5):520.
22. Tischler MD, Lee TH, McAndrew KA, Sax PE, Sutton MS, Lee RT. Clinical, echocardiographic and Doppler correlates of clinical instability with onset of atrial fibrillation. *The American journal of cardiology*. 1990 Sep 15;66(7):721-4.
23. Flaker GC, Fletcher KA, Rothbart RM, Halperin JL, Hart RG. for the Stroke Prevention in Atrial Fibrillation (SPAF) Investigators. Clinical and echocardiographic features of intermittent atrial fibrillation that predict recurrent atrial fibrillation. *Am J Cardiol*. 1995; 76(5):355-8.
24. Lévy S, Maarek M, Coumel P, Guize L, Lekieffre J, Medvedowsky JL, Sebaoun A. Characterization of different subsets of atrial fibrillation in general practice in France: the ALFA study. *Circulation*. 1999 Jun 15;99(23): 3028-35.
25. Singh G, Arora P, Nayyar SB. Study of atrial fibrillation an etiological review. *JAPI*. 2002; 50:1500.
26. Kumar AA, Arora P, Singh G. Clinical profile of atrial fibrillation (AF)-study of 100 cases. *JAPI*. 2002; 50:1558.
27. Timane JM, Hardas MM, Agrawal SS, et al. Atrial fibrillation- A study by colour Doppler - 2D echocardiographic and its correlation with etiology and clinical profile. *JAPI* 2005;53: 324.
28. Kannel WB, Abbott RD, Savage DD, McNamara PM. Epidemiologic features of chronic atrial fibrillation: the Framingham study. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 1982 Apr 29;306(17):1018-22.
29. Henry WL, Morganroth J, Pearlman AS, et al. Relation between echocardiographically determined left atrial size and atrial fibrillation. *Circulation* 1976;53:273-79.
30. Cabin HS, Clubb KS, Hall C, Perlmutter RA, Feinstein AR. Risk for systemic embolization of atrial fibrillation without mitral stenosis. *The American journal of cardiology*. 1990 May 1;65(16):1112-6.
31. Blackshear JL, Pearce LA, Asinger RW, Dittich HC, Goldman ME, Zabalgoitia M, Rothbart RM, Halperin JL, Stroke Prevention in Atrial Fibrillation Investigators. Mitral regurgitation associated with reduced thromboembolic events in high-risk patients with nonrheumatic atrial fibrillation. *The American journal of cardiology*. 1993 Oct 1;72(11):840-3.
32. Sanfilippo AJ, Abascal VM, Sheehan M, Oertel LB, Harrigan P, Hughes RA, Weyman AE. Atrial enlargement as a consequence of atrial fibrillation. A prospective echocardiographic study. *Circulation*. 1990 Sep;82(3):792-7.
33. Banerjee A, Taillandier S, Olesen JB, Lane DA, Lallemand B, Lip GY, et al. Ejection fraction and outcomes in patients with atrial fibrillation and heart failure: the Loire Valley Atrial Fibrillation Project. *Eur J Heart Failure*. 2012;14(3):295-301.
34. Atrial Fibrillation Investigators: Atrial Fibrillation, Aspirin, Anticoagulation Study; European Atrial Fibrillation Study; Stroke Prevention in Atrial Fibrillation Study; Boston Area Anticoagulation Trial for Atrial Fibrillation Study; Canadian Atrial Fibrillation Study; Veterans Affairs Prevention in Atrial Fibrillation Study. Echocardiographic Predictors of Stroke in Patients with Atrial Fibrillation: A Prospective Study of 1066 Patients From 3 Clinical Trials. *Arch Intern Med*. 1998;158(12):1316-20.
35. ul Hassan M, Hussain C, Gul AM, Ullah Jan H, Hafizullah M. Frequency of left atrial and appendage clot in patients with severe mitral stenosis. *J Ayub Med College Abbottabad*. 2010; 22(2):40-2.